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**Non-contractual civil liability for damage caused by AI systems: contributions from
European and Brazilian perspectives**

Dissertation presented as part of the LL.M in International and Comparative Law at Trinity
College Dublin, under the supervision of Prof. Brian Barry

Claudia Silva Battagin

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Summary

This dissertation discusses current approaches in the European Union and Brazil to non-contractual civil liability regarding harm caused by Artificial Intelligence (AI). Although AI is not a recent concept, everyone has felt its rapid development in recent decades. AI represents a world of possibilities and benefits, but, at the same time, it poses risks and significant challenges to society.

The European Union (EU) has recently adopted the most comprehensive regulation for AI so far – the Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA). However, the AIA does not regulate civil liability. This is the subject of two other pieces of proposed legislation: the AI Liability Directive (AILD) and a revision of the Product Liability Directive (rPLD). Combined, these form the missing puzzle piece in the European strategy for AI regulation and have now become the focus of the EU on the AI front. While the AILD directly references the AIA and uses its risk-based approach as a parameter for establishing procedural rules for the disclosure of information of high-risk AI systems, the rPLD applies equally to all AI systems.

Unlike the European approach, other efforts to regulate AI, such as the Brazilian AI Bill (BAIB), focus on one piece of legislation that covers both substantive rules for AI and specific civil liability provisions. Inspired by the AIA, the BAIB also adopts a risk-based approach, albeit tempered with a rights-based approach. The civil liability provisions of the BAIB have changed considerably through the negotiation of the bill, which has yet to be finalised.

This brings us to the central research question of this dissertation: **Is civil liability regulation moving away from the risk categories employed in regulatory frameworks (such as the AIA)? And, if so, should it?**

To address this question, I will first consider the concept of AI systems and to what extent AI challenges existing liability regimes. Next, I will analyse the European approach to AI regulation, from the Resolution adopted by the European Parliament in 2020 to the current approach formed by the AIA, the AILD, and the rPLD. I will then consider the Brazilian approach, comparing two stages of the negotiation of the BAIB that show a change of direction in the strategy for regulating AI civil liability. Drawing from that, I will assess whether AI liability regulation is moving away from the risk categories of regulatory frameworks and whether it should.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	7
2. Regulating AI liability.....	13
2.1. What is an AI system?.....	13
2.2. How do AI systems challenge existing civil liability regimes?.....	17
3. The European Approach to AI Liability.....	20
3.1. The 2020 Resolution of the EU Parliament.....	20
3.2. The AIA and the risk-based approach.....	21
3.3. The AILD.....	24
3.3.1. Disclosure of evidence.....	25
3.3.2. Rebuttable presumptions of fault and causation.....	26
3.4. The rPLD.....	27
3.5. Partial conclusion and critiques.....	31
4. Looking Through the Mirror Glass: the Brazilian Approach to AI Liability.....	35
4.1. A brief overview of the Brazilian non-contractual civil liability system.....	35
4.2. Regulating AI liability in Brazil.....	37
5. Conclusion: To Employ or Not to Employ Risk Categories? That is the Question.....	41
Bibliography.....	47

1. Introduction

In 1609, the philosopher Francis Bacon stated that the ‘mechanical arts are of ambiguous use, serving as well for hurt as for remedy’.¹ This idea remains contemporary when we consider artificial intelligence (AI). While AI may offer new solutions and services that once seemed unattainable (the ‘*remedy*’ or, in everyday language, *benefits*), its new applications raise concerns about the risks and potential harms, particularly to fundamental rights (the ‘*hurt*’ or *risks*).²

Although it is not a new or recent concept, there has been a revolution in using AI in recent decades.³ AI is already part of our daily lives and is used across many sectors.⁴ However, many argue that we are witnessing a ‘Fourth Industrial Revolution’⁵, which marks the beginning of a new chapter for humanity.⁶ The forecast is that, in the coming years, this disruptive technology will increase its impact on our society, fundamentally transforming how we live, work, and interact.⁷

New techniques, such as machine learning and artificial neural networks, are among the factors that allowed for the rapid development of AI in recent decades.⁸ More precisely, it was the combination of such techniques with the evolution of computational data processing

¹ Leon R Kass, ‘The Moral Challenge of Modern Science’ (The New Atlantis, Fall 2006) <<https://www.thenewatlantis.com/publications/the-moral-challenge-of-modern-science>> accessed 28 June 2024.

² Luke Muehlhauser and Ana Salamon, ‘Intelligence Explosion: Evidence and Import’ in Eden A and others (eds), *Singularity Hypotheses: A Scientific and Philosophical Assessment* (Springer 2012) 15-42; David Lorge Parnas, ‘The real risks of artificial intelligence’ (2017) 60 Communications of the ACM 27; Anne-Lise Sibony, ‘Returning to Risk Regulation after a Long Journey’ (2017) 8(1) European Journal of Risk Regulation 112, 113.

³ About the story of AI, see Mariusz Flasiński, *Introduction to Artificial Intelligence* (Springer 2016) 3; Clifford A Pickover, *Artificial Intelligence: An Illustrated History* (Union Square & Co 2019).

⁴ Maciej Jarota, ‘Artificial intelligence in the work process. A reflection on the proposed European Union regulations on artificial intelligence from an occupational health and safety perspective’ (2023) 49 Computer Law & Security Review 105825, 2-3.

⁵ Klaus Schwab, *The Fourth Industrial Revolution* (Portfolio Penguin, London 2024).

⁶ John C Lennox, *2084: Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Humanity* (Zondervan, Grand Rapids 2020).

⁷ Tobias Rothkegel and Mark Taylor, ‘What Characterises Artificial Intelligence and How Does It Work?’ (2016) 22 CTLR 98, 99. For an interesting analysis of possible changes AI may bring over the next 30 years, see Kevin Kelly, *The Inevitable: Understanding the 12 Technological Forces That Will Shape Our Future* (Viking 2016).

⁸ Marcus Ayodeji Araromi, ‘Artificial Intelligence: The Challenges Posed to the Law of Contract in Determining Liabilities of Parties’ (2022) 28 CTLR 87. See also Paulius Cerka, Jurgita Grigiene, and Gintare Sirbikyte, ‘Liability for Damages Caused by Artificial Intelligence’ (2015) 31 Computer Law and Security Review 376, 380; Miriam C Buiten, ‘Towards Intelligent Regulation of Artificial Intelligence’ (2019) 10 Eur J Risk Reg 41.

capabilities and the significant data generated by a society that is, each day, increasingly more engaged in the digital world (*Big Data*⁹).¹⁰

In this context, the civil liability regime applicable to injuries that may arise from AI use remains a pressing and (yet) unsolved issue.¹¹ While civil liability essentially corresponds to the reparation of damage, in a broader view, it is an indispensable instrument for maintaining social order and justice.

To promote the development of trustworthy and safe AI, several jurisdictions have made efforts to regulate AI.¹² Most of these efforts have so far been focused on ethical frameworks and establishing principles applicable to AI development.¹³ The European Union (EU) was the first to go beyond ethical standards and self-regulation to introduce binding rules for AI.¹⁴ After the agreement reached in December 2023 and the endorsement by Parliament in March 2024¹⁵, the Council approved on 21 March 2024 the final version of the much-anticipated and

⁹ Vivienne Artz, 'How "Intelligent" is Artificial Intelligence?' (2019) 20(2) *Privacy & Data Protection* 7, 8. For a technical analysis, see Stuart Russell and Peter Norvig, *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach* (4th edn, Pearson Education 2022) 44.

¹⁰ Schwab (n 5) 22.

¹¹ For example, a survey conducted in 2020 concluded that concerns with AI liability were seen as the most relevant external obstacle for companies to use AI (European Commission, 'European Enterprise Survey on the Use of Technologies Based on Artificial Intelligence: Final Report' (Publications Office of the European Union 2020) <<https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/f089bbae-f0b0-11ea-991b-01aa75ed71a1>> accessed 28 June 2024).

¹² Mireille Hildebrandt, 'Artificial Intelligence Law' in Jan M Smits, Jaakko Husa, Catherine Valcke and Madalena Narciso (eds), *Elgar Encyclopedia of Comparative Law* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2023) 139-152.

¹³ Dimitar Lilkov, 'Regulating Artificial Intelligence in the EU: A Risky Game' (2021) 20(2) *European View* 166, 167. See, also: Jessica Fjeld and others, 'Principled Artificial Intelligence: Mapping Consensus in Ethical and Rights-Based Approaches to Principles for AI' (Berkman Klein Center Research Publication, 2020-1) <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3518482> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁴ European Commission, 'Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts' COM (2021) 206 final.

¹⁵ European Parliament, 'Artificial Intelligence Act: MEPs Adopt Landmark Law' (European Parliament, 13 March 2024) <<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240308IPR19015/artificial-intelligence-act-meps-adopt-landmark-law>> accessed 28 June 2024.

negotiated Artificial Intelligence Act (AIA¹⁶).¹⁷ The AIA will likely be published in the Official Journal of the EU any day now and will enter into force 20 days later.¹⁸

The AIA adopts a risk-based approach, categorising AI systems into different levels of risk and imposing corresponding obligations on their providers and users.¹⁹ However, it does not determine who will be liable if damage occurs due to AI use. The strategy adopted by the EU in regulating AI is threefold: a package composed of a regulatory framework focused on prevention and safety rules in general (represented by the AIA), the update of specific safety product legislation (currently ongoing), and the update of the civil liability regime applicable to AI-related harm – the latter is the topic of this dissertation.²⁰

The debates on regulating AI civil liability in the EU have been ongoing for at least half a decade²¹, and the need to make amendments to the existing liability regimes has been recognised numerous times.²² In February 2020, the EU Commission published a White Paper proposing initial criteria for distinguishing high-risk and non-high-risk AI systems and imposing corresponding obligations.²³ This White Paper was accompanied by a report prepared

¹⁶ In this dissertation, it is the text approved by the Council on 21 March 2024 that is referred to here as the ‘AIA’ (Council of the European Union, ‘Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts’ PE-24-2024-INIT [hereinafter AIA]).

¹⁷ Council of the European Union, ‘Artificial Intelligence Act: Council Gives Final Green Light to the First Worldwide Rules on AI’ (Council of the European Union, 21 May 2024) <<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/05/21/artificial-intelligence-ai-act-council-gives-final-green-light-to-the-first-worldwide-rules-on-ai/>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁸ With some provisions of the AIA adopting a different timeline for entering into force.

¹⁹ About using a risk-based approach in general, see Robert Baldwin, Martin Cave, and Martin Lodge, *Understanding Regulation: Theory, Strategy, and Practice* (Martin Cave ed, 2nd edn, Oxford University Press 2012) 81-86, 281-95.

²⁰ Herbert Zech, ‘Liability for AI: public policy considerations’ (2021) 22 ERA Forum 147, 150.

²¹ For example, in 2018, the Commission issued a Staff Working Document on Liability for Emerging Digital Technologies (European Commission, ‘Liability for emerging digital technologies’ SWD(2018) 137 final (Staff Working Document) <<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52018SC0137>> accessed 28 June 2024).

²² See, for example, Andrea Bertolini, ‘Artificial Intelligence and Civil Liability’ (European Parliament, JURI Study, Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs, 2020) PE 621.926 <[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/621926/IPOL_STU\(2020\)621926_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2020/621926/IPOL_STU(2020)621926_EN.pdf)> accessed 28 June 2024 [hereinafter EP JURI Study]; European Parliament, ‘Resolution of 20 October 2020 with Recommendations to the Commission on a Civil Liability Regime for Artificial Intelligence’ 2020/2014(INL) <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2020-0276_EN.html#title1> accessed 28 June 2024 [hereinafter 2020 Resolution]; Expert Group on Liability and New Technologies, ‘Liability for Artificial Intelligence and Other Emerging Digital Technologies’ (European Commission 2019) <<https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/regexpert/index.cfm?do=groupDetail.groupMeetingDoc&docid=36608>> accessed 28 June 2024 [hereinafter Liability Expert Group Report].

²³ European Commission, ‘On Artificial Intelligence – A European Approach to excellence and trust’ COM (2020) 65 final (White Paper) <https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/white-paper-artificial-intelligence-european-approach-excellence-and-trust_en> accessed 28 June 2024 [hereinafter White Paper].

by the Commission examining the implication of AI for existing liability systems and identifying potential gaps.²⁴

In October of the same year, the EU Parliament adopted a resolution containing detailed recommendations for regulating AI civil liability (2020 Resolution).²⁵ The 2020 Resolution proposed the adoption of two different civil liability regimes for harm caused by AI systems, depending on the level of risk posed by such systems: as a rule, high-risk AI systems would be subject to strict liability, while other AI systems would be subject to a fault-based liability regime, with a presumption of fault combined with the reversal of the burden of proof, unless Member States adopted stricter national laws.²⁶ This regime would apply in parallel to product liability law, which should be updated through the review of the Product Liability Directive of 1985 (1985 PLD)²⁷, in a manner closely coordinated regarding the substance and approach of the 2020 Resolution.²⁸

In September 2022, while the AIA was being negotiated, the EU Commission published two proposals relevant to AI liability: the AI Liability Directive (AILD)²⁹ and a revision of the 1985 PLD (rPLD)³⁰. Combined, these directives form the missing puzzle piece in the European strategy for AI regulation and have now become the focus of the EU on the AI front.³¹ The rPLD was approved by Parliament on 12 March 2024 and is currently under review by the Council for future publication, which should not take long.³² The AILD, however, has yet to be voted by Parliament.

²⁴ European Commission, 'Report on the safety and liability implications of Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things and robotics' (COM/2020/64 final), available on: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0064>.

²⁵ 2020 Resolution (n 22).

²⁶ 2020 Resolution (n 22), Recitals 13, 17, Arts 3, 8.

²⁷ Council Directive 85/374/EEC of 25 July 1985 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States concerning liability for defective products, OJ L 210/29, 7 August 1985 [hereinafter 1985 PLD].

²⁸ 2020 Resolution (n 22), Recital 23.

²⁹ European Commission, 'Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Adapting Non-Contractual Civil Liability Rules to Artificial Intelligence (AI Liability Directive)' COM (2022) 496 final [hereinafter AILD].

³⁰ European Commission, 'Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Liability for Defective Products' COM (2022) 495 final [hereinafter rPLD].

³¹ Philipp Hacker, 'The European AI Liability Directives – Critique of a Half-Hearted Approach and Lessons for the Future' (2023) 51 Computer Law & Security Review 105871 3-4.

³² European Parliament, 'Defective Products: Revamped Rules to Better Protect Consumers from Damages' (European Parliament, 12 March 2024) <<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press->

The strategy adopted in the AILD and the rPLD, jointly considered, is significantly different than that of the 2020 Resolution. The AILD applies to non-contractual fault-based civil law claims for injuries caused by AI systems. It focuses solely on harmonising procedural aspects across the Member States' tort law. It introduces rules authorising the disclosure of information for high-risk AI systems and rebuttable presumptions of fault and/or causation in certain situations. The AILD relies on the AIA for the definition of AI systems, high-risk AI systems, and other concepts.

On the other hand, the rPLD does not rely on the AIA or its risk categories. It applies to 'products', encompassing both 'traditional' products (non-digital) and software in general, AI included. Liability under the rPLD is triggered by defectiveness. Similar to the 1985 PLD, the rPLD does not affect national rules governing non-contractual liability for situations not involving defective products. The rPLD eases the burden of proof for victims under specific conditions, incorporating provisions for evidence disclosure and presumptions of defectiveness in cases of non-compliance with disclosure obligations, violation of safety law requirements, or obvious product malfunction. However, these presumptions do not relate specifically to AI or the risk categories of the AIA.

This brings us to our central research question: **Is civil liability regulation moving away from the risk categories employed in regulatory frameworks (such as the AIA)? And, if so, should it?**³³

To tackle this question, this dissertation is divided into four parts. Following this Introduction, Chapter 2 very briefly discusses the definition of AI systems and the challenges that AI might pose for existing liability regimes. Chapter 3 contains an overview of the European approach to AI liability, addressing the AIA, the AILD and the rPLD, and comparing them to the 2020 Resolution, while also presenting relevant critiques.

room/20240308IPR18990/defective-products-revamped-rules-to-better-protect-consumers-from-damages>
accessed 28 June 2024.

³³ This dissertation focuses exclusively on non-contractual civil liability. Any reference to 'civil liability' or simply 'liability' should be understood to pertain solely to non-contractual civil liability, unless otherwise specified by the context.

Chapter 4 introduces a comparative perspective to the research question³⁴, by considering the Brazilian AI regulation, namely Law No. 2,338/2023 (BAIB).³⁵ It aims to verify how another jurisdiction that also opted for a risk-based approach is currently regulating liability and whether the risk categories established in the legislation have been adopted as a parameter for establishing different liability regimes.

Drawing from the analysis in Chapters 3 and 4, Chapter 5 concludes this dissertation, addressing whether AI liability regulation is moving away from the risk categories of regulatory frameworks and whether it should.

³⁴ This dissertation does not intend to present complete comparative research on AI liability between the EU and Brazil. The regulation of AI in Brazil is much more incipient than in the EU, as the BAIB has not yet been finalised nor subject to voting in either chamber of the Brazilian Parliament. It's still unclear when it will come into effect and, more importantly, what its final text will be. Furthermore, although interesting, complete and adequate comparative research between the EU and Brazil would require not only the selection of a specific jurisdiction within the EU for comparative purposes - especially considering the many differences in concepts of tort law across the Member States - but also a comprehensive analysis of the tort law and product liability systems adopted in each jurisdiction, which escapes the focus of this dissertation.

³⁵ Brazilian Federal Senate, Bill No. 2,338 of 2023 <<https://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/157233>> accessed 28 June 2024 [hereinafter BAIB].

2. Regulating AI Liability

Before addressing the current approaches to AI liability, it is necessary to introduce some general concepts and reflect on the reasons for and purpose of regulating AI liability in a broader perspective. This chapter will present brief remarks on the definition of AI systems (1.1) and the challenges it might pose for existing liability regimes (1.2).

2.1. What is an AI system?

Defining AI or AI systems is a challenging task. It's a matter of great debate that is immensely relevant to society and that encompasses knowledge - and points of view - from many different fields, ranging from computer science (*is this artificial intelligence?*) to biology and neuroscience (*does this mirror human intelligence?*), philosophy (*what is intelligence in the first place?*), sociology (*how does this affect humans and society?*), law (*should we regulate this?*) and so many others.

While this dissertation won't delve into the details of the debate, from a legal point of view, it's essential to acknowledge the significance of these concepts for the analysis of AI liability. For example, as will be addressed in Chapter 2, under the current European approach, a victim of harm caused by an AI system will be subject to a different liability regime than a victim of harm caused by software in general (not embedded with AI). Thus, grasping the concept of an AI system is essential to understanding when a different liability regime, if any, should apply.

At first glance, AI systems could be defined as 'machines' or systems capable of emulating human intelligence. For instance, the Oxford Dictionary defines AI as '[t]he theory and development of *computer systems able to perform tasks normally requiring human intelligence*, such as visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation between languages'.³⁶

³⁶ Elizabeth M Knowles (ed), *Oxford Dictionary of Phrase and Fable* (2nd edn, Oxford University Press 2005) Oxford Reference Collection
<<https://www.oxfordreference.com/display/10.1093/acref/9780198609810.001.0001/acref-9780198609810-e-423>> accessed 28 June 2024 (emphasis added).

However, as Russell and Norvig explain, AI has been defined throughout history using four different approaches.³⁷ Some have argued that AI corresponds to computers or machines which try to emulate human beings' thought processes.³⁸ Others focused on the external behaviour of the AI while still using humans as a parameter.³⁹ For them, an AI should act like a human being, and a system would only be an AI if it could pass the tests created by Alan Turing (the Turing Tests⁴⁰).⁴¹

Other scholars have preferred not to use human intelligence as the parameter for AI systems because of the vagueness around the concept of 'intelligence'.⁴² Instead, they refer to an abstract notion called 'rationality', which involves logic and rational thinking.⁴³ As a result, AI could either be understood as systems that *think* logically or that *act* rationally. The latter, the most prevalent approach to AI, focuses on the system 'doing the right thing', 'according to the information ... provide[d]' and the available resources.⁴⁴

The difference between these lines of thought becomes more apparent when one examines some attempts at defining AI. For instance, John McCarthy, the 'father' of the term AI stated that the 'ultimate effort is to make computer programs that can *solve problems and achieve goals* in the world *as well as humans*'.⁴⁵ McCarthy's definition of AI seems to lean more towards seeing AI as trying to think or act like humans.

A different approach was taken, for example, on the Report prepared by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence:

³⁷ Russel and Norvig (n 9) 19. See also Matt O'Shaughnessy, 'One of the Biggest Problems in Regulating AI Is Agreeing on a Definition' (*Carnegie Endowment for International Peace*) <<https://carnegieendowment.org/2022/10/06/one-of-biggest-problemsin-regulating-ai-is-agreeing-on-definition-pub-88100>> accessed 28 June 2024.

³⁸ Russel and Norvig (n 9) 20, 21.

³⁹ *ibid* 19.

⁴⁰ The computer will pass the test if a human interrogator, after asking some written questions, cannot determine whether the written responses come from a person or not (Alan M Turing, 'Computing Machinery and Intelligence' (1950) 59(236) *Mind* 433-460).

⁴¹ Russel and Norvig (n 9) 19.

⁴² High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence, 'A Definition of Artificial Intelligence: Main Capabilities and Scientific Disciplines' (European Commission, 2019) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/definition-artificial-intelligence-main-capabilities-and-scientific-disciplines>> accessed 28 June 2024.

⁴³ *ibid* 21.

⁴⁴ *ibid* 22.

⁴⁵ John McCarthy, 'What Is Artificial Intelligence?' (Technical report, Stanford University 2007) <<http://jmc.stanford.edu/artificial-intelligence/what-is-ai/index.html>> accessed 28 June 2024 (emphasis added).

Artificial intelligence (AI) systems are software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information, derived from this data and deciding the *best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal*.⁴⁶

Although a rational AI system always tries to choose the ‘best’ action, it will not always succeed from a human being’s perspective. This may be due to many reasons, from computational limitations to rational failures in the ‘instructions’ provided by the AI developer or the user. For example, if an automated vehicle is designed to avoid exposing its user to any risk at all times without exceptions, it would never take the user anywhere and probably never leave the garage. After all, although perhaps absurd for a human being and indeed incompatible with modern life, this would probably be the most rational decision if one is to avoid risks at all costs. This is usually referred to as ‘bounded rationality’.⁴⁷

While functioning, an AI system perceives the environment around it, collects and interprets data, reasons on the interpreted information according to the established parameters, decides the best course of action and acts on it, possibly modifying its environment.⁴⁸ A *learning* rational system evaluates how the environment has been affected by its previous actions and then *adapts its behaviour to better achieve its goal*.⁴⁹ This resembles the concept of machine learning.

Although many confuse and mix both concepts, machine learning and artificial intelligence are not synonyms. The former is an AI technique that permits machines to learn from data and generate output based on this acquired knowledge instead of solely being programmed to perform a specific task.⁵⁰ There are several approaches to machine learning and

⁴⁶ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (n 42) 1. Similarly, Jacob Turner defines AI as ‘the ability of a non-natural entity to make choices by an evaluative process’ (Jacob Turner, *Robot Rules: Regulating Artificial Intelligence* (Palgrave Macmillan, London 2019) 16).

⁴⁷ High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence (n 42) 3.

⁴⁸ *ibid* 1-2.

⁴⁹ *ibid* 3.

⁵⁰ For a technical analysis, see Russel and Norvig (n 9) 669-733. See also Harry Surden, ‘Machine Learning and Law’ (2014) 89 *Washington Law Review* 87; Julie Mehan, *Artificial Intelligence: Ethical, social, and security impacts for the present and the future* (IT Governance Publishing, 2022) 19.

other related learning techniques, such as decision trees, neural networks, and deep learning, which add more complexity to AI systems.⁵¹

From all these concepts, different techniques, and approaches, it is possible to conclude that there isn't a precise unique definition of AI. Naturally, this vagueness presents a significant challenge for regulation.

While the AIA does not define the term 'artificial intelligence', the definition of an AI system was one of the most significant discussions during the legislative process. The original proposal defined AI systems as software developed with the techniques and approaches listed in Annex I, which included machine learning, knowledge-based, and statistical approaches. However, the vagueness of the term and the possibility of it being applied to a wide range of applications that are not necessarily compatible with the concept of AI as an 'intelligent machine' gave rise to significant critiques.⁵² After intense debate in the legislative process, the final text adopted the following definition:

An AI system is a machine-based system designed to operate with *varying levels of autonomy* and that *may exhibit adaptiveness after deployment* and that, *for explicit or implicit objectives, infers*, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments.⁵³

This new definition has been received with much more enthusiasm than its predecessor.⁵⁴ While it is not exempt from criticism⁵⁵, it reaches a balanced approach between making a definition that is too broad or too narrow. More importantly, it does not focus on the technology itself – the method or approach adopted in creating the system – but on its purpose and key features. However, the open concept of AI and the general lack of knowledge of people of what AI is will probably still be the source of significant discussions in the near future as to whether specific AI-related provisions apply to particular systems.

⁵¹ Buiten (n 8) 41; Araromi (n 8) 87. For a technical analysis, see Russel and Norvig (n 9) 675-733, 801-836.

⁵² Hacker (n 31) 8. See also: Michael Veale and Frederik Zuiderveen Borgesius, 'Demystifying the Draft EU Artificial Intelligence Act - Analysing the good, the bad, and the unclear elements of the proposed approach' (2021) 22 Computer Law Review International 97.

⁵³ AIA (n 16), Art 3 (1) (emphasis added).

⁵⁴ See, for example, Stibbe, 'The EU Artificial Intelligence Act: Our 16 Key Takeaways' (Stibbe, 2023) <<https://www.stibbe.com/publications-and-insights/the-eu-artificial-intelligence-act-our-16-key-takeaways>> accessed 28 June 2024.

⁵⁵ Martin Ebers, 'Truly Risk-Based Regulation of Artificial Intelligence - How to Implement the EU's AI Act' (2024) SSRN <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=4870387>> accessed 28 June 2024, 18.

2.2. How do AI systems challenge existing civil liability systems?

Two characteristics that are expressly mentioned in the AIA's definition of AI systems are their ability to operate with 'varying levels of *autonomy*' and 'exhibit *adaptiveness*'. Many scholars claim that these characteristics and other recurring features of some AI systems - such as complexity, opacity, unpredictability, and data dependency - represent potential challenges for civil liability regimes.⁵⁶

Tort law addresses civil claims that do not involve contractual obligations and come into play when a person experiences injury or harm due to another individual's actions or lack thereof.⁵⁷ Tort law varies considerably from jurisdiction to jurisdiction, even among the EU's Member States.⁵⁸ If a fault-based regime is employed, it generally requires the claimant to prove that the defendant owed a duty of care, breached that duty, and that the breach caused harm or injury that led to financial losses or damages. In a strict liability regime, the element of fault is removed from the equation, but proof of damage and causation remains crucial.

The level of autonomy of AI systems is directly related to possible unpredictable behaviour. AI systems may lead to outputs unforeseeable by humans, even software engineers who designed them in the first place.⁵⁹ Truly 'autonomous' and 'unforeseeable' behaviour by AI systems may represent a significant – or perhaps even prohibitive – challenge to proving

⁵⁶ Gyandeep Chaudhary, 'Artificial Intelligence: The Liability Paradox' (2020) *ILI Law Review Summer Issue* 144 <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=3845397>> accessed 28 June 2024; Henry Fraser and others, 'AI Opacity and Explainability in Tort Litigation' (2020) *Journal of Law and Technology* 1; Philipp Hacker and others, 'Explainable AI under Contract and Tort Law: Legal Incentives and Technical Challenges' (2020) 28 *Artificial Intelligence and Law* 415 <<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-020-09260-6>> accessed 28 June 2024; Baris Soyer and Andrew Tettenborn, 'AI and Civil Liability: Do We Need a New Regime?' (2021) *Lloyd's Maritime and Commercial Law Quarterly* 12, 14; Beatrice Schütte and others, 'Damages Liability for Harm Caused by AI' (2022) *European Journal of Law and Technology* 34, 36; Marek Swierczynski, 'Liability for AI: Main Challenges of the EU' (2022) *European Review of Private Law* 45.

⁵⁷ About the interaction between tort law and AI, see Horst Eidenmüller, 'The Rise of Robots and the Law of Humans' (2017) 27 *Oxford Legal Studies Research Paper* 1 <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=2941001>> accessed 28 June 2024.

⁵⁸ For a detailed analysis, see Cees Van Dam, *European Tort Law* (2nd edn, Oxford University Press 2013); Ernst Karner, Bernhard A. Koch, and Mark A. Geistfeld, 'Comparative Law Study on Civil Liability for Artificial Intelligence' (Publications Office of the European Union 2021) <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/definition-artificial-intelligence-main-capabilities-and-scientific-disciplines> accessed> 28 June 2024.

⁵⁹ Philip Hacker described autonomy as 'independence from human intervention coupled with a quasi-cognitive learning and/or adaptation capacity' (Hacker (n 31) 4). See also Matthew U Scherer, 'Regulating Artificial Intelligence Systems: Risks, Challenges, Competences, and Strategies' (2016) 29(2) *Harvard Journal of Law & Technology* 354, 365; Roman V. Yampolskiy, 'Unpredictability of AI: On the Impossibility of Accurately Predicting All Actions of a Smarter Agent' (2020) 7 *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Consciousness* 109.

fault in negligence claims.⁶⁰ However, the challenge goes beyond the difficulty of proving fault. The issue of foreseeability also impacts causation.⁶¹ It may be excessively difficult for a harmed individual to prove that the specific input for which the developer, for instance, is at fault caused the specific output that led to the damage.⁶²

Another potential challenge is that AI systems may exhibit different opacity and complexity levels, particularly those that use self-learning algorithms.⁶³ This entails that explaining or finding a reason for certain decisions may be nearly impossible.⁶⁴ The ‘black box’ nature of some AI systems can make it challenging for victims to establish fault and causation, leading to uncertainty regarding the interpretation and application of existing national liability laws in AI-related cases.⁶⁵

Opacity, however, may also arise from ‘intentional corporate or institutional self-protection and concealment’ due to providers having complete control over the data and information.⁶⁶ Naturally, this also leads to harmed individuals having extreme difficulty accessing sufficient information about AI systems to base their claims.⁶⁷

Another issue comes not from the design of the algorithms that form the AI system but from data used in its training. Many AI systems use vast amounts of data to function. If the training data is biased, the AI system will perpetuate such bias in its outputs.⁶⁸ A clear example is that of AI systems used for hiring or promoting employees, which must consider how the

⁶⁰ Soyer and Tettenborn (n 56) 6; Joel Castillo González, ‘Products liability in Europe and the United States’ (2012) *Revista Chilena de Derecho* 39 (2) 292; Mark Chinen, ‘The Co-Evolution of Autonomous Machines and Legal Responsibility’ (2016) 20 *Virginia Journal of Law & Technology* 339, 342.

⁶¹ Miquel Martín Casals, ‘Causation and Scope of Liability in the Internet of Things (IoT)’ in Sebastian Lohsse, Rainer Schulze and Dirk Staudenmayer (eds), *Liability for Artificial Intelligence and the Internet of Things* (Hart 2019) 221.

⁶² Chinen (n 60) 343. Yavar Bathaee, ‘The Artificial Intelligence Black Box and The Failure of Intent and Causation’ (2018) 31(2) *Harvard Journal of Law & Technology* 889, 891.

⁶³ Jenna Burrell, ‘How the machine “thinks”’: Understanding opacity in machine learning algorithms’ (2016) 3 *Big Data & Society* 2053951715622512; Zachary C Lipton, ‘The mythos of model interpretability: In machine learning, the concept of interpretability is both important and slippery’ (2018) 16 *Queue* 31.

⁶⁴ Burrell (n 63) 10; Alejandro Barredo Arrieta and others, ‘Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI): Concepts, taxonomies, opportunities and challenges toward responsible AI’ (2020) 58 *Information Fusion* 82.

⁶⁵ Explanatory Memorandum of the AILD (n 29) 2. See also EP JURI Study (n 22) 33.

⁶⁶ Burrell (n 63) 10; Ulla-Maija Mylly, ‘Transparent AI? Navigating between Rules on Trade Secrets and Access to Information’ (2023) 54(7) *IIC* 1013, 1014.

⁶⁷ Bernhard Koch and others, ‘Response of the European Law Institute to the Public Consultation on Civil Liability – Adapting Liability Rules to the Digital Age and Artificial Intelligence’ (2022) 13 *Journal of European Tort Law* 25, 43-46.

⁶⁸ Ziad Obermeyer and others, ‘Dissecting Racial Bias in an Algorithm Used to Manage the Health of Populations’ (2019) 366 *Science* 447.

training data may impact people with ‘sensitive attributes such as age, disability, gender, religion or belief, racial or ethnic origin, or sexual orientation’.⁶⁹ While liability is, in principle, possible, proving the bias would not be easy, rendering compensation nearly impossible.⁷⁰ For instance, if the human resources department of a company employs a biased AI system in its selection of candidates, it’s highly improbable that individuals could know about, let alone prove, the discriminatory nature of the AI system or the intent or negligence of the AI provider.

Other factors not explicitly related to the technology also make determining AI liability difficult and complex, such as the involvement of multiple economic actors and the complexity of the relationship among them. This might lead victims to have problems in identifying the liable party.⁷¹

Tasked with analysing how AI systems challenge liability regimes, the Expert Group on Liability and New Technologies – New Technologies Formation concluded that the current non-contractual liability regimes of the Member States ensure *basic* protections for victims of harm caused by new technologies, including AI. However, due to specific characteristics of AI systems, victims injured by AI could be in a less favourable position than when no AI was involved.⁷²

As a result, the Liability Expert Group Report recommended that ‘certain adjustments need to be made to EU and national liability regimes’.⁷³ The details of how these adjustments have been carried out in the EU will be discussed in the next chapter.

⁶⁹ Alessandro Fabris and others, ‘Fairness and Bias in Algorithmic Hiring’ (2023) ACM Cornell University <<https://arxiv.org/abs/2309.13933>> accessed 28 June 2024, 5.

⁷⁰ Peggy Valcke, Aleksandra Kuczerawy and Pieter-Jan Ombelet, ‘Supervising automated journalists in the newsroom: liability for algorithmically produced news stories’ (2016) 61 *Revue de Droit des Technologies de l’Information* 5, 9-12, 15-17.

⁷¹ Gerald Spindler, ‘User Liability and Strict Liability in the Internet of Things and for Robots’ in Sebastian Lohsse, Rainer Schulze and Dirk Staudenmayer (eds), *Liability for Artificial Intelligence and the Internet of Things* (Hart 2019) 128, 130. See also EP JURI Study (n 22) 56.

⁷² Liability Expert Group Report (n 22).

⁷³ *ibid* 3.

3. The European Approach to AI Liability

This chapter will consider the European approach to AI civil liability, comparing the original proposal contained in the 2020 Resolution (2.1) to the current system composed by the joint reading of the AIA (2.2), the AILD (2.3) and the rPLD (2.4).

3.1. The 2020 Resolution of the European Parliament⁷⁴

In October 2020, the EU Parliament published the 2020 Resolution, recommending the Commission to draft rules for a civil liability regime for AI to prevent the fragmentation of the digital single market and to eliminate obstacles for individuals who have been harmed and wish to pursue legal action against AI providers in cross-border situations.⁷⁵

The 2020 Resolution suggested that liability for AI should be based on the idea that ‘whoever creates, maintains, controls or interferes with the AI-system, should be accountable for the harm or damage that the activity, device or process causes’.⁷⁶ It recommended the adoption of two different civil liability regimes for harm caused by AI systems, depending on the level of risk posed by such systems: high-risk AI systems should be subject to strict liability, while other AI systems should be subject to a fault-based liability regime, with a presumption of fault combined with the reversal of the burden of proof, unless Member States adopted stricter national laws.⁷⁷

To rebut the presumption of fault, the AI provider would need to prove either that **(1)** the AI system was ‘activated without his or her knowledge while all reasonable and necessary measures to avoid such activation ... were taken’; or **(2)** they had acted diligently by ‘selecting a suitable AI-system for the right task and skills, putting the AI-system duly into operation, monitoring the activities and maintaining the operational reliability by regularly installing all available updates’.⁷⁸

⁷⁴ For a comprehensive commentary on the 2020 Resolution, see Nikos Th Nikolinakos, ‘Adapting the EU Liability Regime to Artificial Intelligence (AI): The European Commission’s Proposed Policy Options’ (2022) 28 *Computer and Telecommunications Law Review* 66.

⁷⁵ 2020 Resolution (n 22) 26.

⁷⁶ *ibid* Recital 8.

⁷⁷ *ibid* Arts 3, 8, Recitals 13, 17.

⁷⁸ *ibid* Art 8 (2).

Strict liability would also apply for applications that the Commission had not yet assessed as high-risk but ‘caused repeated incidents resulting in serious harm or damage’.⁷⁹ This regime would apply parallel to product liability law, which should be updated through the review of the 1985 PLD in a manner closely coordinated with the 2020 Resolution.⁸⁰

While the 2020 Resolution defined ‘high-risk’⁸¹, it did not provide specific details of how to distinguish high-risk and non-high-risk AI systems. It recommended all high-risk AI systems be exhaustively listed in an annexe to the regulation, which the Commission should constantly review.⁸²

Finally, another important aspect of the 2020 Resolution is that it suggested that AI liability regulation should cover harm or damage to life, health, physical integrity, property, and immaterial harm that resulted in a significant verifiable economic loss.⁸³

3.2. The AIA and the risk-based approach

A few months after the publication of the 2020 Resolution, the European Commission introduced the AIA to create a harmonised framework for regulating AI use and creation within the EU.⁸⁴ According to the explanatory memorandum, its fundamental purpose is to ‘ensure that AI systems placed on the Union market and used are safe and respect existing law on fundamental rights and Union values’.⁸⁵ After a long negotiation process, the Council approved the final version of the AIA on 21 March 2024.⁸⁶ It will be published in the Official Journal of the EU any day now and will enter into force 20 days after publication, with different timelines for some obligations.

⁷⁹ *ibid* 21

⁸⁰ *ibid*, Recital 23.

⁸¹ *ibid*, Art 3 (c).

⁸² *ibid*, Recital 14.

⁸³ *ibid* Recital 16, Arts 2(1), 5.

⁸⁴ AIA (n 16), Art 1(1).

⁸⁵ Explanatory memorandum of the AIA (n 16) 3.

⁸⁶ Council of the European Union, ‘Artificial Intelligence Act: Council Gives Final Green Light to the First Worldwide Rules on AI’ (Council of the European Union, 21 May 2024) <<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/en/press/press-releases/2024/05/21/artificial-intelligence-ai-act-council-gives-final-green-light-to-the-first-worldwide-rules-on-ai/>> accessed 28 June 2024.

The AIA adopts a risk-based approach, categorising AI systems into risk⁸⁷ levels and imposing corresponding obligations for each category.⁸⁸ Although the AIA only expressly refers to ‘prohibited practices’ and ‘high-risk AI systems’, it creates four different risk categories commonly referred to as ‘unacceptable risk’, ‘high-risk’, ‘limited-risk’ and ‘minimum risk’ AI systems.⁸⁹ On the one end of the spectrum, the AIA prohibits unacceptable risk systems⁹⁰, while, on the other end, it recommends that the so-called ‘minimal risk’ systems adopt and comply with voluntary conduct codes.⁹¹

While high-risk and limited-risk AI systems must comply with specific obligations created by the AIA, the obligations imposed on the former are much more stringent. Limited-risk AI systems must only comply with the transparency obligations of Article 50, mainly ensuring that users know that they are interacting with an AI system.⁹² High-risk AI systems, on the other hand, must undergo *ex ante* conformity assessments and comply with several *ex post* obligations, such as implementing quality management systems, conducting risk assessments, maintaining detailed documentation, establishing a robust system for monitoring and reporting incidents, and ensuring transparency by providing clear information about the system’s capabilities and limitations, among others.⁹³

The parameters for establishing these risk categories do not consider the technology employed but the potential use of the AI system. Prohibited unacceptable risk systems are listed in eight categories in Article 5, including, for example, systems capable of monitoring and profiling natural persons, and manipulating persons through subliminal techniques.

High-risk AI systems are defined in Articles 6 and 7. An AI system will be considered high-risk if: **(1)** it is intended to be used as a safety component of a product, or is itself a product,

⁸⁷ According to the AIA, a risk is ‘the combination of the probability of an occurrence of harm and the severity of that harm’ (AIA (n 16), Art 3(2)).

⁸⁸ For more details on the risk-based approach, see Chris Holder, ‘The Commission’s Proposed Artificial Intelligence Regulation’ (2021) 27 *Comp Tel L Rev* 130; W. Gregory Voss, ‘AI Act: The European Union’s Proposed Framework Regulation for Artificial Intelligence Governance’ (2021) 25 *Journal of Internet Law*, 8-12; Vera Lúcia Raposo, ‘Ex Machina: Preliminary Critical Assessment of the European Draft Act on Artificial Intelligence’ (2022) *Int J Law Inf Technol* 88; Tobias Mahler, ‘Between Risk Management and Proportionality: The Risk-Based Approach in the EU’s Artificial Intelligence Act Proposal’ in *Nordic Yearbook of Law and Informatics 2020–2021: Law in the Era of Artificial Intelligence* (2022) 247–270 <<https://doi.org/10.53292/208f5901.38a67238>> accessed 28 June 2024. For a critical assessment, see Ebers (n 55).

⁸⁹ *Lilkov* (n 13) 168.

⁹⁰ AIA (n 16), Art 5.

⁹¹ *ibid* Recital 20, Art 95.

⁹² *ibid* Art 50.

⁹³ *ibid* Arts 8-50.

regulated by the Union harmonising legislation listed in Annex II and has undergone a third-party conformity assessment (for example, medical devices and toys)⁹⁴; or **(2)** it is used in the sectors listed in Annex III, which currently includes eight items⁹⁵.

An AI system listed in Annex III of the AI Act will not be classified as high-risk if it does not pose a significant threat to health, safety, or fundamental rights, and does not substantially influence decision-making outcomes.⁹⁶ This exception applies if the AI system is designed for a narrow procedural task, enhances the results of a previously completed human activity, identifies decision-making patterns without replacing human judgment, or performs a preparatory task for assessments related to Annex III use cases.⁹⁷ However, any AI system that profiles individuals is always considered high-risk.⁹⁸

There are three types of limited-risk AI systems addressed in Article 50: **(1)** those designed to interact with natural persons⁹⁹; **(2)** those capable of emotion recognition or biometric categorisation¹⁰⁰; and **(3)** those that generate or manipulate image, audio, or video content¹⁰¹. Some examples are chatbots and visual or audio deepfake content.

By default, systems not included in the previously mentioned categories are classified as minimal risk, assuming they pose little or no threat to fundamental rights. This group, so far, comprehends most existing AI systems, such as AI-enabled photo-editing software, product-recommender systems, and spam-filtering software.

The diffusion of ChatGPT and other similar models led to the creation of a new category called ‘general-use AI models’ (GPAI). This category, which was heavily discussed during the negotiation of the AIA, encompasses tools commonly referred to as ‘foundation models’ or ‘large generative models’.¹⁰² The AIA distinguishes between general obligations for all GPAI

⁹⁴ AIA (n 16), Art 6(1).

⁹⁵ *ibid* Art 6(1) and 6(2).

⁹⁶ *ibid* Art 6(3).

⁹⁷ *ibid*.

⁹⁸ *ibid*.

⁹⁹ *ibid* Art 50(1).

¹⁰⁰ *ibid* Art 50(3) and 50(4).

¹⁰¹ *ibid* Art 50(2).

¹⁰² See, for example, Philipp Hacker, Andreas Engel and Marco Mauer, ‘Regulating ChatGPT and other Large Generative AI Models’ (2023) ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '23) 1112; Natali Helberger and Nicholas Diakopoulos, ‘ChatGPT and the AI Act’ (2023) 12 Internet Policy Review.

and additional obligations for those with systemic risks.¹⁰³ GPAI models with systemic risks are subject to stringent obligations, including model evaluations, risk assessments, incident reporting, and cybersecurity measures.¹⁰⁴

As anticipated, despite being a comprehensive regulation, the AIA does not regulate civil liability. This is the subject of the AILD and the rPLD, which will be analysed in the following sections.

3.3. The AILD

The AILD applies to non-contractual fault-based civil law claims arising from harm caused by AI systems. The AILD does not explicitly define the term ‘fault’, thus allowing Member States to apply the concepts derived from their traditional tort law regimes, which may vary in meaning and requirements.¹⁰⁵

There are important limits to the scope of the AILD, namely **(1)** liability in the field of transport¹⁰⁶; **(2)** rights under the 1985 PLD¹⁰⁷; **(3)** exemptions from liability and obligations under the Digital Services Act¹⁰⁸⁻¹⁰⁹; and **(4)** ‘national rules determining which party has the burden of proof, which degree of certainty is required as regards the standard of proof, or how fault is defined, other than in respect of what is provided for in Articles 3 and 4’.¹¹⁰ The latter is complemented by the provision in Article 1(4), which states that the Member States are free to adopt or maintain liability rules that are more favourable for claimants in AI-related claims as long as they are compatible with Union law.¹¹¹ In practice, Member States can apply different liability rules, such as strict liability, if they wish.

¹⁰³ AIA (n 16) Arts 51- 53.

¹⁰⁴ *ibid* Art 55.

¹⁰⁵ Van Dam (n 58) 225-228.

¹⁰⁶ AILD (n 29) Art 1(3)(a).

¹⁰⁷ *ibid* Art 1(3)(b).

¹⁰⁸ Regulation (EU) 2022/2065 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 October 2022 on a Single Market for Digital Services and amending Directive 2000/31/EC, OJ L 277 (Digital Services Act).

¹⁰⁹ AILD (n 29) Art 1(3)(c).

¹¹⁰ *ibid* Art 1(3).

¹¹¹ *ibid* Art 1(4).

The AILD applies to claims involving providers and users, as defined in the AIA.¹¹² The AILD mainly refers to procedural elements. As detailed below, it introduces rules authorising the disclosure of information for high-risk AI systems (2.3.1) and rebuttable presumptions of fault and/or causation in certain situations, including violations of the AIA (2.3.2).

3.3.1. Disclosure of information

Article 3 of the AILD empowers courts to order the disclosure or preservation of information about high-risk AI systems upon the request of a claimant or a potential claimant.¹¹³ There are some requirements for the request to be successful, which vary slightly if it is, in fact, a claimant or a potential claimant. Claimants must prove that they have ‘undertaken all proportionate attempts at gathering the relevant evidence from the defendant’.¹¹⁴ On the other hand, potential claimants must first request the same information from the provider or the user and, second, instruct the request with ‘facts and evidence sufficient to support the plausibility of a claim for damages’.¹¹⁵

Courts should only order the disclosure or preservation of information considered ‘necessary and proportionate to support a potential claim or a claim for damages’.¹¹⁶ Jan de Bruyne and others highlight that the concepts of ‘necessary’ and ‘proportionate’ will need to be applied following national law, which may ‘potentially result in different/ diverging approaches’.¹¹⁷

Additionally, the AILD provides that courts should consider all legitimate interests involved in determining whether a disclosure order is proportionate, including the need to protect trade secrets and confidential information.¹¹⁸ Specific measures should be taken to

¹¹² *ibid* Art 2(3), 2(4).

¹¹³ *ibid* Art 3.

¹¹⁴ *ibid* Art 3(2).

¹¹⁵ *ibid* Art 3(1).

¹¹⁶ AILD (n 29) Art 3(4).

¹¹⁷ Jan De Bruyne, Orian Dheu, and Charlotte Ducuing, ‘The European Commission’s Approach to Extra-Contractual Liability and AI – An Evaluation of the AI Liability Directive and the Revised Product Liability Directive’ (2023) 51 *Computer Law & Security Review* 105894, 5.

¹¹⁸ *ibid*.

preserve confidentiality when the disclosure of a trade secret (or alleged trade secret) is ordered.¹¹⁹

3.2.2. Rebuttable presumptions of fault and causation

If a defendant fails to comply with a disclosure order for evidence at its disposal, the AILD introduces a rebuttable presumption of non-compliance with a duty of care, ‘in particular in the circumstances referred to in Article 4(2) or (3)’, which essentially corresponds to a substantive violation of the AIA by the provider, or the user, each in different circumstances.¹²⁰ The defendant may rebut that presumption by submitting evidence to the contrary.¹²¹

The AILD introduces another rebuttable presumption in Article 4, but this time targeting causality rather than fault. Three requirements must be met:

- (i) The claimant must have proved, or the court must have presumed (due to failure to comply with a disclosure order) that the defendant failed to comply with a duty of care laid down in Union or national law directly intended to protect against the damage that occurred.
- (ii) It is *reasonably likely* that the defendant’s fault *influenced* the output produced by the AI system or the failure of the AI system to produce an output; and
- (iii) The claimant must have proved that this output (or lack thereof) gave rise to the damage.

For high-risk AI systems, the AILD typically requires a substantive violation of the AI Act for these procedural mechanisms to come into play.¹²² This rationale follows the previous recommendation made by scholars, who argued for a correlation between the violation of substantive AI regulation and procedural alleviations of burden¹²³. However, this conception of fault overlooks the possibility of harm even when an AI system complies with the AIA.¹²⁴ If fault is confined to non-compliance with the AIA, victims of harm caused by compliant high-

¹¹⁹ *ibid.*

¹²⁰ AILD (n 29) Art 3(5).

¹²¹ *ibid.*

¹²² *ibid* Art 4(2).

¹²³ Zech (n 29) 152-153.

¹²⁴ Article 67(1) of the AIA (n 16) recognises that compliant AI systems may still pose risks to the health or safety of individuals and their fundamental rights.

risk AI would be unable to seek compensation for the harm endured since the AILD would not be applicable.

If sufficient evidence is available to the claimant, the presumption of a causal link may not apply. Conversely, for non-high-risk AI systems, the presumption applies only if proving causation is excessively difficult for the claimant. The presumption can also be rebutted if the defendant can provide contrary evidence.

Having considered the AILD, the next section will address the remaining piece of legislation in the AI liability front in the EU: the rPLD.

3.4. The rPLD

The review of the 1985 PLD is part of the EU strategy for regulating AI. However, the rPLD does not apply solely to AI systems; it encompasses all sorts of products and now includes software and digital manufacturing files. As a result, the revision of the 1985 PLD is focused not only on AI but also on addressing some issues and trends in EU product legislation.

The rPLD does not expressly reference the AIA or its risk-based categories. The provisions of the rPLD apply in theory equally to all AI systems, regardless of the category in which they were included under the AIA. This is one of the most critical differences from the AILD.

Similar to the 1985 PLD, the rPLD creates an obligation for Member States to ensure that any harm caused by a defective product will be subject to compensation.¹²⁵ It also does not affect national rules establishing non-contractual liability for situations not involving defective products.¹²⁶ The rPLD and the AILD apply in parallel and, according to the European Commission, without overlap.¹²⁷ Conversely to the AILD, the rPLD provides for full

¹²⁵ rPLD (n 30), Art 3.

¹²⁶ *ibid* Art 2.

¹²⁷ Explanatory Memorandum to the rPLD (n 30) 4.

harmonisation between Member States, following the position adopted by the CJEU in numerous case laws pertaining to the scope of application of the 1985 PLD.¹²⁸

The rPLD extends the previous protection afforded to injured persons in three manners. Firstly, the rPLD extended its material scope of application.¹²⁹ For instance, the concept of product is widened to include software and digital manufacturing files¹³⁰; the loss of data is included in the definition of damage¹³¹; and the manufacturer now remains liable even after the product or service has been placed on the market, as long as they are within the manufacturer's control¹³².

The material scope of application of the 1985 PLD has been the subject of a long debate, specifically, if standalone software (and not as a product component) qualified as a product.¹³³ The rPLD resolves such debate by expressly including software and digital manufacturing files in the definition of 'product'. However, it is worth noting that, unlike the AILD, the rPLD does not apply solely to AI systems but more generally to software, including AI. This is another important difference from the AILD.

Secondly, the rPLD broadens the scope of people subject to product liability. The 1985 PLD applies to 'producers' of defective products, which are generally the 'manufacturer of a finished product, any raw material or the manufacturer of a component part' and may, in certain

¹²⁸ See, for example, Case C-52/00: Commission of the European Communities v French Republic ECLI:EU:C:2002:252 paras. 13 et seq.; CJEU, Case C-154/00, Commission v. Greece, ECLI:EU:C:2002:254 paras. 9 et seq.

¹²⁹ Henrique Sousa Antunes, 'Non-contractual Liability Applicable to Artificial Intelligence: Towards a Corrective Reading of the European Intervention' (2023, forthcoming) in Luisa Antonioli and Paola Iamiceli (eds), *The Making of European Private Law: Changes and Challenges* (University of Trento) <<https://ssrn.com/abstract=4351910>> accessed 28 June 2024, 4.

¹³⁰ rPLD (n 30), Art 4(1).

¹³¹ *ibid*, Art 4(6), (7).

¹³² *ibid*, Art 1(e).

¹³³ Geraint Howells, Christian Twigg-Flesner and Chris Willett, 'Product liability and digital products' in Tatiana-Eleni Synodinou and others (eds), *EU Internet Law* (Springer 2017); Fairgrieve and Eleonora Rajneri, 'Is Software a Product under the Product Liability Directive?' (2019) 1 *Zeitschrift für Internationales Wirtschaftsrecht* 24; Christiane Wendehorst, 'Safety and Liability Related Aspects of Software' (July 2021) 64-66; Bernhard Koch and others, 'Response of the European Law Institute to the Public Consultation on Civil Liability – Adapting Liability Rules to the Digital Age and Artificial Intelligence' (2022) 13 *Journal of European Tort Law* 25, 31-37; Jan De Bruyne and others, 'Tort Law and Damage Caused by AI Systems' in Jan De Bruyne and Cedric Vanleenhove (eds), *Artificial Intelligence and the Law* (Intersentia 2022) 417-421.

situations, also be the importer, the product supplier, or any person putting their name or trademark in the product.¹³⁴

While the rPLD also applies to the manufacturer of defective products or components, other ‘economic operators’ listed in Article 7 may become liable under certain conditions, such as the ‘fulfilment service providers’¹³⁵, distributors, or providers of online platforms allowing consumers to conclude distance contracts.¹³⁶ The rPLD also expands the concept of manufacturers to include any ‘natural or legal person that modifies a product that has already been placed on the market or put into service’, as long as that modification is ‘substantial’ and is outside the control of the original manufacturer.¹³⁷ However, unlike the AILD, claims under the rPLD are restricted to the economic operators in the supply chain. Business users and consumers are not subject to product liability.

Thirdly, the rPLD changes the existing rules or creates new mechanisms to facilitate compensation for victims. For instance, the rPLD eases the burden of proof for victims under specific conditions, incorporating provisions for evidence disclosure and presumptions of defectiveness in cases of non-compliance with disclosure obligations, violation of safety law requirements, or obvious product malfunction.¹³⁸ These ‘burden alleviation mechanisms’ have no direct relation to the risk categories of the AIA. They apply equally to high-risk and non-high-risk AI systems. They are, however, restricted to complex software systems.

Another important difference is that, similarly to the 1985 PLD, liability under the rPLD is triggered solely by the defectiveness of a product and the causal link between the damage suffered and the defective product, irrespective of whether the defect is attributable to the producers’ fault. While product liability is generally perceived as a strict liability system, some elements resemble a negligence rule, particularly the test required to define a defective product¹³⁹.

¹³⁴ 1985 PLD (n 27), Art 3.

¹³⁵ The former include anyone in business offering ‘at least two of the following services: warehousing, packaging, addressing and dispatching of a product, without having ownership of the product, with the exception of postal services’ (rPLD (n 30), Art 7(4)).

¹³⁶ *ibid* Art 7(3).

¹³⁷ *ibid* Art 7(4).

¹³⁸ *ibid* Arts 8, 9.

¹³⁹ Zech (n 29) 150.

As explained by McMahon & Binchy, '[t]he notion of defectiveness clearly does not require proof of negligence on the part of the producer, yet, because of the reference to the reasonable expectations of "a person" (in essence, a consumer expectation test), the difference between negligence and strict liability is not that pronounced'.¹⁴⁰ Therefore, product liability tends towards strict liability if a defect is easily identifiable. Conversely, difficulty in proving the defectiveness of a product makes product liability akin to negligence liability. Thus, the concept of a 'defect' is crucial in determining 'how strict' the strict liability under product liability really is.

The rPLD continues to rely on the consumer-expectation test as the defining criteria for a defective product.¹⁴¹ That is to say, a product is considered defective if it fails to provide the safety that a person is entitled to expect, considering all circumstances, including the time in which the product was put into circulation.

However, the rPLD overlooks a crucial aspect regarding the defectiveness of AI systems: AI models can make unique mistakes that are not typically made by humans¹⁴². This raises questions about whether such flaws constitute a defect under product liability law and whether human conduct should be considered as a parameter for assessing the existence of a defect. If so, the system could be considered defective if an average human would not have made the mistake, or, at least, if consumers would have expected an average human not to make such a mistake. However, the problem arises if it is practically impossible to avoid specific errors arising from rare and unpredictable conditions under which humans could also make mistakes.

For instance, let's consider that a company hires employees to act on customer service and receive calls from annoyed customers with complaints about the company's service. The employees are responsible for listening to the customers, summarising the complaints, and categorising them into groups. Let's suppose there is a 40% margin of error in the categorisation made by humans. The company, aiming to make the process faster and more accurate,

¹⁴⁰ McMahon & Binchy, *Casebook on the Irish Law of Torts* (3rd edition, Tottel Publishing, West Sussex, 2005) 305.

¹⁴¹ Howells & Weatherill, *Consumer Protection Law* (Ashgate Publishing, Aldershot, 2005) 216; Mathias Reimann, 'Liability for Defective Products at the Beginning of the Twenty-First Century: Emergence of a Worldwide Standard?' (2003) 51 *The American Journal of Comparative Law* 768-769; Owen, Montgomery & Davis, *Products Liability and Safety – Cases and Materials* (Foundation Press, 6th Edition, Thomson Reuters, New York, 2010) 241-265.

¹⁴² For an interesting example involving self-driving cars, see Hacker (n 31) 15.

implements software developed by another company that uses AI to classify complaints. After implementing the AI software, the overall error margin drops to 20%. However, some of the categorisation errors are so obvious that they would not typically be committed by human beings.

In this hypothetical example, is it possible to conclude that the software presents a defect concerning these specific errors that humans would not commit, even if we consider that its error margin is well above the human parameter? Adopting an anthropomorphic standard would result in a defect in the software. This solution, however, may impose a threshold too high for software and AI developers, resulting in over-deterrence.

On the other hand, adopting what is referred to by scholars as a ‘system-oriented approach’¹⁴³, the defectiveness of the product would not be analysed in the individual case but considering its overall performance. A defect would only exist if the malfunction was present at the systemic level.¹⁴⁴

While the rPLD imposes liability based on defectiveness and causation, challenges arise in applying traditional consumer expectation tests to AI-related claims due to the unique nature of AI systems. Further detailing the concept of defectiveness for software within the rPLD would be ideal.

Finally, although it now covers data loss and corruption, the damage covered by the rPLD remains limited if compared to tort law regimes in general. Damage means material losses resulting from death or bodily injury, destruction of any property other than the defective product, products damaged by a defective component, and property used exclusively for professional purposes. Cases of pure economic loss, for example, remain outside the scope of the rPLD.

2.5. Partial conclusion

Some of the notable distinctions between the AILD and the rPLD are:

¹⁴³ Hacker (n 31) 15.

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

- (i) ***The fundamental criteria for triggering liability:*** The AILD applies for fault-based civil liability claims under the Member State’s tort law, while the rPLD is rooted in EU law and requires establishing the product’s defectiveness, not fault.
- (ii) ***The relationship with the AIA:*** While the AILD references the AIA and uses its risk categories to establish different procedural mechanisms applicable to claims involving high-risk AI systems, the rPLD follows a different direction without differentiating among AI systems.
- (iii) ***Compensable damage:*** The rPLD limits eligible damage to property, death or personal injury, and data loss. Under the AILD, compensable damage will vary according to the Member State’s tort law regime, but is generally wider and may include, for example, pure economic loss.
- (iv) ***The scope:*** The AILD focuses solely on harmonising procedural rules (disclosure of information and certain presumptions of fault or causation) for fault-based claims involving AI systems. It aims not to interfere with the Member States’ tort law systems, leaving it open for each country to apply their national system or create stricter AI civil liability rules, provided they comply with the minimum requirements of the AILD and the rPLD. The rPLD, on the other hand, expands the material scope of product liability (namely the concept of ‘products’ to include ‘software’) and the list of liable actors (the now-called ‘economic operators’), and creates presumptions of defectiveness and causation applicable in certain situations, regardless of the risk posed by the AI system.

While achieving a harmonised European tort liability regime may seem beyond immediate reach, harmonising the approach to AI liability was feasible and desirable, particularly considering the EU Parliament’s recommendations in the 2020 Resolution.

Some scholars claim that this ‘dualistic’ approach, adopted by the European Commission, would be preferable to developing a unique AI liability regime for the EU.¹⁴⁵ They argue that it would simultaneously preserve the diversity and coherence of national tort law systems across Member States.¹⁴⁶ Jan de Bruyne argues that this option would be more adequate as it does not ‘overhaul the liability frameworks already in place’ and, as a result, ‘prevent[s] complexification and also potentially avert[s] any legal incoherence and unbalances from

¹⁴⁵ Beatrice Schütte and others (n 56) 23; Jan De Bruyne, Elias Van Gool and Thomas Gils, ‘Tort Law and Damage Caused by AI Systems’ in Jan De Bruyne and Cedric Vanleenhove (eds), *Artificial Intelligence and the Law* (Intersentia 2022) 395.

¹⁴⁶ Miriam Buiten, Alexandre de Streeel and Martin Peitz, ‘EU Liability Rules for the Age of Artificial Intelligence’ (Centre on Regulation in Europe, 9 April 2021) 59.

occurring due to the uncertain interaction between a European legal instrument and existing national strict liability regimes'.¹⁴⁷

However, even if this one unified coherent framework was indeed not achievable, at the very least, these two directives should have aligned closely in terms of content, facilitating the implementation of consistent procedural mechanisms in similar circumstances. As where we stand today, the current proposals of the AILD and the rPLD do not reach that goal.

Despite the European Commission's assertion that there is no intended overlap between claims under the rPLD and the AILD, practical instances of overlap are inevitable, particularly in cases involving harm caused by products incorporating AI systems. In these cases, individuals seeking redress will need to select either the legal framework of the rPLD or of the AILD, as adopted in their respective national legislations, or both. This might lead to problems in identifying the correct applicable regime. For instance, Philip Hacker raises concerns that some companies may falsely claim to utilise AI when, in reality, they are relying on standard software or marginally complex algorithms. This distinction becomes critical in cases where an injured party seeks compensation through the AILD: if the alleged company's use of AI is not true, the claim could theoretically be dismissed, as the AILD requires explicit AI involvement, whereas the rPLD covers general software.¹⁴⁸

Furthermore, the current lack of consistency between the fault-based regime proposed in the AILD and the non-fault-based framework of the rPLD may lead to unjust outcomes for victims, since the higher protection is contingent upon the potential application of the rPLD, which, on the other hand, has a more limited scope of application.

Finally, a closer inspection of the AILD reveals that it has not gone too far from the general principle in tort law that a claimant bears the burden of proof. On one hand, the scope of the mechanism for evidence disclosure is limited to information 'at the disposal' of the AI provider, making it difficult for individuals to assess the completeness and relevance of the provided evidence. On the other, even if individuals successfully obtain evidence, the technical

¹⁴⁷ Jan De Bruyne, Elias Van Gool and Thomas Gils, 'Tort Law and Damage Caused by AI Systems' in Jan De Bruyne and Cedric Vanleenhove (eds), *Artificial Intelligence and the Law* (Intersentia 2022) 395, 399.

¹⁴⁸ Hacker (n 31) 6.

complexity of the information may hinder their ability to interpret it effectively, necessitating expert assistance that may be financially burdensome.¹⁴⁹

While procedural alleviation mechanisms like evidence disclosure and presumption of causality aim to facilitate proving fault and causation, their limitations may render them ineffective in addressing the challenges victims face when seeking compensation for AI-related harm. An alternative approach would involve either expanding the scope of procedural alleviation mechanisms to cover all AI systems or even adopting distinct mechanisms (such as shifting the burden of proof, for example) in different circumstances (which may or may not correspond to the risk categories of the AIA).

¹⁴⁹ EP JURI Study (n 22) 84.

4. Looking Through the Mirror Glass: the Brazilian Approach to AI Liability

Moving temporarily away from the EU, this chapter will focus on the current Brazilian AI regulation, Bill No. 2338/2023 (BAIB).¹⁵⁰ The BAIB mirrors the AIA in some respects, including its risk-based approach, but unlike the AIA, it specifically regulates AI civil liability.

The approach of the BAIB to AI liability initially resembled the EU 2020 Resolution, proposing different liability regimes according to the risk categories. However, on 18 June 2024, the liability provisions radically changed, distancing themselves from the risk categories. This scenario makes Brazil an exciting example for the subject matter of this dissertation.

This chapter is divided into two parts. The first will outline introductory concepts regarding the civil liability system in Brazil to allow for a better understanding of the provisions in the BAIB (3.1). The second will consider the general structure of the BAIB and the civil liability provisions (3.2).

4.1. A brief overview of the Brazilian non-contractual civil liability system

Brazil follows the civil law tradition. Non-contractual civil liability is partially governed by sections 186 and 927 of the Brazilian Civil Code (Law No. 10,406/2002)¹⁵¹, which establish a fault-based approach or a general ‘subjective rule’ (as called in Portuguese).¹⁵² This requires the tortfeasor to have acted (or failed to act) with either fault or intent. Fault *stricto sensu* encompasses negligence, recklessness, and malpractice.

The Brazilian civil liability system has experienced significant transformations in the last century, which led to the adoption of the risk theory, the emergence of strict liability, and the decline of the relevance of fault in general.¹⁵³ It currently employs both fault-based and strict

¹⁵⁰ Brazilian Senate, 'Bill No. 2338, of 2023: Provides for the use of Artificial Intelligence' (2023) <<http://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/157233>> accessed 28 June 2024. For an unofficial translation of the original text, see Baptista Luz Advogados, ‘Draft Bill of Legislation Proposing the New Brazilian Artificial Intelligence Act: Overview of the Proposal and Next Steps’ (Baptista Luz Advogados, 2023) <<https://www.baptista.com.br/draft-bill-of-legislation-proposing-the-new-brazilian-artificial-intelligence-act-overview-of-the-proposal-and-next-steps/?lang=en>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁵¹ Brazil, Law No. 10.406, 10 January 2002, Establishes the Civil Code, Official Gazette of the Union, Section 1, 11 January 2002, p 1 <https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/leis/2002/110406compilada.htm> accessed 28 June 2024 [hereinafter Brazilian Civil Code].

¹⁵² Sílvio de Salvo Venosa, *Direito Civil: Obrigações e Responsabilidade Civil* (vol 2, Grupo GEN 2023) 370.

¹⁵³ Alvinio Lima, *Culpa e risco* (2nd edn, RT 1999) 118 et seq.; Claudio Luiz Bueno de Godoy, *Responsabilidade pelo risco da atividade: uma cláusula geral no Código Civil de 2002* (Saraiva 2009) 13.

liabilities, with the former being generally regarded as the rule and the latter being applied in three scenarios: **(1)** when provided by specific laws, such as transport, environmental damage, consumer law, etc.; **(2)** when the activity typically conducted by the author of the damage, by its nature, represents a risk to others (this is often referred to as a ‘dangerous activity’¹⁵⁴); and **(3)** when someone abuses their rights, manifestly exceeding statutory limits¹⁵⁵.

For someone to be held liable, whether through fault-based or strict liability, the victim must prove three elements¹⁵⁶: conduct (act or omission), damage¹⁵⁷, and a causal link between such damage and the tortfeasor’s conduct¹⁵⁸. The difference between the two modalities of liability lies in the requirement (or lack thereof) of fault or intent in the tortfeasor’s conduct.

One of the statutes that opted for a strict liability system is the Consumer Defence Code (Law No. 8,078/1990), which regulates product liability law.¹⁵⁹ It imposes strict liability on manufacturers, producers, constructors, and importers of products and services for any defects that cause harm to consumers. Similarly to the 1985 PLD, it requires proof of defect of the product or service. However, unlike the 1985 PLD, damage under product liability law in Brazil is not limited to cases involving death or physical injury. It covers a wide range of situations, including pure economic loss and psychological harm.¹⁶⁰

Bearing these concepts in mind, the next topic will consider the Brazilian approach to AI regulation.

¹⁵⁴ Sérgio Cavalieri Filho, *Programa de Responsabilidade Civil* (16th edn, Grupo GEN 2023) 5.

¹⁵⁵ Daniel M Boulos, *Abuso do Direito no novo Código Civil* (Método 2006) 135-137.

¹⁵⁶ Maria Helena Diniz, *Curso de direito civil brasileiro: Responsabilidade civil* (vol 7, Grupo GEN 2023) 20.

¹⁵⁷ Damage may be material or immaterial. The former encompasses actual loss (emerging damages) and any amount the victim reasonably expected but failed to earn (lost profits), including pure economic loss. Immaterial damage corresponds to the injury of non-pecuniary interests (i.e. pain or suffering that intensely interferes with the individual’s psychological behaviour). In addition to proving the tortfeasor’s unlawful act and damage, the victim must also prove that there is a causal link between them. The threshold for proving causation is high. The most accepted theories are ‘adequate causation’ and ‘direct and immediate damage’. For more details, see Cavalieri (n 154) 93; Venosa (n 152) 391-398.

¹⁵⁸ The threshold for proving causation in Brazil is high. The most accepted theories are ‘adequate causation’ and ‘direct and immediate damage’. For more details, see Cavalieri (n 154) 63-65.

¹⁵⁹ Brazil, Consumer Protection Code (Law No. 8.078, 11 September 1990) https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L8078compilado.htm accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶⁰ Clarissa Costa Lima, ‘Dos vícios dos produtos no Novo Código Civil e no CDC e suas repercussões no âmbito da responsabilidade civil’ (2003) 51 *Revista de Direito do Consumidor* 116.

4.2. Regulating AI liability in Brazil

Brazil started walking the path to AI regulation in 2019.¹⁶¹ Since then, numerous proposals have been submitted to Parliament, with the approach towards AI liability changing substantially over time.

The first Bill introduced (Bill 5,015/2019) was broad and merely ascribed civil liability for AI-related harm to its ‘supervisor’.¹⁶² The second Bill (Bill 21/2020)¹⁶³ was slightly more detailed. It established that AI developers and operators should be liable based on fault, unless it involved consumer relations, to which strict liability would apply. Although heavily criticised¹⁶⁴, Bill 21/2020 was approved by the Deputies Chamber, one of the Houses of Parliament, in September 2021.¹⁶⁵

While it was under analysis by the Senate, lawyers and academic community members addressed an ‘open letter’ to the Senate stressing many problems with the liability regime chosen for AI.¹⁶⁶ As a result, the Parliament decided to set up a temporary committee of legal experts to study the issue and propose a new draft bill.

¹⁶¹ For a detailed analysis of the Brazilian Strategy for AI, see Luca Belli, Yasmin Curzi, Walter B. Gaspar, ‘AI Regulation in Brazil: Advancements, Flows, and the Need to Learn from the Data Protection Experience’ (2023) 48 *Computer Law & Security Review* 105767 5-9; João Roman, ‘Artificial Intelligence in Brazil: the Brazilian Strategy for AI and Bill 21/2020’ (Institute for Research on Internet and Society, 5 October 2021) <<https://irisbh.com.br/en/artificial-intelligence-in-brazil-the-brazilian-strategy-for-artificial-intelligence-bsai-ebia-and-bill-no-21-2020/>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶² Brazilian Federal Senate, Bill No. 2338/2023 (Senado Federal, 2023) <<https://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/138712>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶³ Chamber of Deputies, ‘Legal Framework for Artificial Intelligence - Bill No. 21-A of 2020 - Final Draft Approved by the Chamber of Deputies and Sent to the Senate’ (Chamber of Deputies, 2020) <https://www.camara.leg.br/proposicoesWeb/prop_mostrarintegra?codteor=2129459> accessed 28 June 2024.

For an unofficial translation, see CyberBRICS, ‘Non-Official Translation of the Brazilian Artificial Intelligence Bill No. 21/2020’ (CyberBRICS, 2020) <<https://cyberbrics.info/non-official-translation-of-the-brazilian-artificial-intelligence-bill-n-21-2020/>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶⁴ Walter Gaspar and Yasmin Curzi, ‘Artificial Intelligence in Brazil Still Lacks a Strategy’ (Report by the Center for Technology and Society at FGV Law School, May 2021) <<https://cyberbrics.info/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/EBIA-en-2.pdf>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶⁵ Chamber of Deputies, ‘Chamber Approves Bill Regulating the Use of Artificial Intelligence’ (Chamber of Deputies, 29 September 2021) <<https://www.camara.leg.br/noticias/811702-camara-aprova-projeto-que-regulamenta-uso-da-inteligencia-artificial/>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶⁶ Consultor Jurídico, ‘Especialistas criticam responsabilidade subjetiva prevista no PL do marco da IA’ [‘Experts Criticize the Subjective Liability Provided in the AI Framework Bill’] (Consultor Jurídico, 27 October 2021) <<https://www.conjur.com.br/2021-out-27/especialistas-questionam-artigo-pl-marco-legal-ia>> accessed 28 June 2024.

In December 2022, the committee delivered a report with its main findings to the Senate, accompanied by a draft bill.¹⁶⁷ Based on this draft, in May 2023, Senator Rodrigo Pacheco presented Bill No. 2,338/2023 (BAIB).

The BAIB is inspired by the AIA and the 2020 Resolution. It mirrors the AIA by adopting a risk-based approach, albeit tempered with a rights-based approach.¹⁶⁸ The BAIB categorises AI systems according to different levels of risk, namely excessive-risk, high-risk and other AI systems. Excessive-risk systems, as specified in Article 14, are prohibited. High-risk AI systems are detailed in Article 18 and subject to stringent obligations. The exact content of each risk tier is still under discussion. However, for now, they are pretty similar to the AIA's unacceptable and high-risk categories.¹⁶⁹

The BAIB's initial approach to liability resembled the 2020 Resolution. It proposed different liability regimes according to the risk categories. AI provider or user should be held liable for any damages caused, regardless of the system's autonomy. For high or excessive risk¹⁷⁰ systems, liability should be strict. For other systems, fault would be presumed, along with a reversal of the burden of proof. The Consumer Defence Code should continue to apply to consumer relations, even for harm caused by AI systems.

In August 2023, the Senate set up an internal commission on AI to examine the proposal of the BAIB, amendments to this proposal¹⁷¹, and any other bills¹⁷¹ proposed in the meantime (Internal Commission). On 7 and 18 June 2024, the Internal Commission published two reports

¹⁶⁷ Brazil, STJ, 'Ministro Cueva entrega proposta de regulação da inteligência artificial ao presidente do Senado' ['Minister Cueva Delivers Proposal for AI Regulation to Senate President'] (STJ, 7 December 2022) <<https://www.stj.jus.br/sites/portalp/Paginas/Comunicacao/Noticias/2022/07122022-Ministro-Cueva-entrega-proposta-de-regulacao-da-inteligencia-artificial-ao-presidente-do-Senado.aspx>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶⁸ Ana Frazão, 'Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in Brazil: Examination of Draft Bill No. 2338/2023' (2024) 10(1) UNIO - EU Law Journal 55-70 <https://www.camara.leg.br/proposicoesWeb/prop_mostrarintegra?codteor=2129459> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁶⁹ *ibid* 15.

¹⁷⁰ 'Excessive risk' is the term employed by the BAIB to refer to prohibited systems, which, comparing to the AIA, would be the 'unacceptable risk AI systems'.

¹⁷¹ Up until the submission of this dissertation, 6 (six) amendments referred to the civil liability provisions, namely Amendments No. 1, 46, 47, 50, 70, and 90 (Astronauta Marcos Pontes, 'Emenda 1 ao PL 2338' (2024); Weverton, 'Emenda 46 ao PL 2338' (2024); Alessandro Vieira, 'Emenda 47 ao PL 2338' (2024); Rogério Carvalho, 'Emenda 50 ao PL 2338' (2024); Astronauta Marcos Pontes, 'Emenda 70 ao PL 2338' (2024); Laércio Oliveira, 'Emenda 90 ao PL 2338' (2024)). Available at <https://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/157233#tramitacao_10754739> accessed 28 June 2024.

containing preliminary conclusions, accompanied by amended drafts of the BAIB.¹⁷² The Internal Commission used the proposal of the BAIB as the basis and suggested important alterations to the text.

The liability provisions have radically changed. A complete comparison between the original version of the BAIB and its latest version can be seen in the table below:

Original draft of the BAIB¹⁷³	Draft accompanying the Internal Commission's report of 18 June 2024 (Amended BAIB)¹⁷⁴
Article 27. The provider or operator of an artificial intelligence system that causes property, moral, individual, or collective damage is obliged to fully compensate for it, regardless of the system's degree of autonomy.	Article 35. Civil liability arising from damage caused by artificial intelligence systems within consumer relations remains subject to the liability rules provided in Law No. 8,078, of September 11, 1990 (the Consumer Defence Code) and the relevant legislation, without prejudice to the application of other provisions of this Law.
§1 When dealing with a high-risk or excessive-risk artificial intelligence system, the provider or operator shall be strictly liable for the damage caused, to the extent of their participation in the damage.	Article 36. Civil liability arising from damage caused by artificial intelligence systems exploited, employed, or used by artificial intelligence agents remains subject to the liability rules provided in Law No. 10,406, of January 10, 2002 (Civil Code) and special legislation, without prejudice to the application of other provisions of this Law.
§2 When the system is not considered high-risk, the fault of the agent who caused the damage will be presumed, with the burden of proof being reversed in favour of the victim.	Sole Paragraph. The concrete definition of the civil liability regime applicable to damage caused by AI systems must take into account the following criteria, unless otherwise specified by law: I – the level of autonomy of the artificial intelligence system and its degree of risk, as defined by this law; and

¹⁷² Brazilian Senate, 'Report No. __, of 2024 from the Temporary Committee on Artificial Intelligence in Brazil, concerning various Bills on the use and regulation of Artificial Intelligence' (2024) <https://legis.senado.leg.br/sdleg-getter/documento?dm=9640105&ts=1719507063983&rendition_principal=S&disposition=inline> accessed 28 June 2024; Brazilian Senate, 'Report No. __, of 2024 from the Temporary Committee on Artificial Intelligence in Brazil, concerning various Bills on the use and regulation of Artificial Intelligence' (2024) <https://legis.senado.leg.br/sdleg-getter/documento?dm=9640105&ts=1719507063983&rendition_principal=S&disposition=inline> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁷³ Brazilian Senate, 'Bill No. 2338, of 2023: Provides for the use of Artificial Intelligence' (2023) <<http://www25.senado.leg.br/web/atividade/materias/-/materia/157233>> accessed 28 June 2024. For an unofficial translation of the original text, see Baptista Luz Advogados, 'Draft Bill of Legislation Proposing the New Brazilian Artificial Intelligence Act: Overview of the Proposal and Next Steps' (Baptista Luz Advogados, 2023) <<https://www.baptista.com.br/draft-bill-of-legislation-proposing-the-new-brazilian-artificial-intelligence-act-overview-of-the-proposal-and-next-steps/?lang=en>> accessed 28 June 2024.

¹⁷⁴ Translated by this author from the original document in Portuguese. Brazilian Senate, 'Report No. __, of 2024 from the Temporary Committee on Artificial Intelligence in Brazil, concerning various Bills on the use and regulation of Artificial Intelligence' (2024) <https://legis.senado.leg.br/sdleg-getter/documento?dm=9640105&ts=1719507063983&rendition_principal=S&disposition=inline> accessed 28 June 2024.

	II – the nature of the involved agents and the consequent existence of a specific civil liability regime in the legislation.
<p>Article 28. Artificial intelligence agents will not be held liable when:</p> <p>I – they prove that they did not put the artificial intelligence system into circulation, use it, or benefit from it; or</p> <p>II – they prove that the damage [was] caused exclusively by the victim’s or a third party’s fault and by an external act of God (force majeure/fortuitous case events).</p>	<p>Article 37. The judge shall reverse the burden of proof when the victim is vulnerable or when the AI system’s characteristics make it excessively burdensome for the victim to prove the requirements of civil liability.</p>
<p>Article 29. The instances of civil liability arising from damage caused by artificial intelligence systems within consumer relations remain subject to the rules provided in Law No. 8,078, of September 11, 1990 (Consumer Defence Code), without prejudice to the application of other provisions of this Law.</p>	<p>Article 38. Participants in the regulatory sandbox for artificial intelligence remain liable, under the applicable legislation, for any damages inflicted on third parties as a result of experimentation conducted within the sandbox environment.</p>

The amended version of the BAIB reinforces existing tort law and product liability law - neither specifically designed nor adapted for AI - and specifies that the assessment of the liability regime applicable to damage caused by AI systems requires the courts to consider the AI system’s autonomy and its ‘degree of risk’, along with the nature of the agents involved. Additionally, it provides that the burden of proof shall be reversed when the victim is vulnerable or when the characteristics of the AI system’s operation make it excessively burdensome for the victim to prove the civil liability requirements.

The Internal Commission’s work is still ongoing. Only upon finalisation of its work and voting will a new consolidated version of the BAIB be published, scrutinised, and, then, voted on in both Houses of the Brazilian Parliament before being subject to approval by the President. It’s still unclear when it will come into effect and, more importantly, what its final text will be.¹⁷⁵

¹⁷⁵ Some claim that the BAIB will be voted on by Parliament in July, but this seems highly unlikely to me. See further: Gazeta do Povo, 'Senado Deve Votar Regulamentação da IA Antes do Recesso, Diz Pacheco' (Gazeta do Povo, 2023) <<https://www.gazetadopovo.com.br/república/senado-deve-votar-regulamentacao-da-ia-antes-do-recesso-diz-pacheco/>> accessed 28 June 2024.

5. Conclusion: To Employ or Not to Employ Risk Categories for Liability, That is the Question

Updating liability rules considering AI faces a significant challenge: reaching a - perhaps impossible? - balance between compensating victims of unjust harms and preventing over-regulation of technology, which might stifle innovation and the development of AI.

In the Introduction, I have stated the central research question of this dissertation. Now, it's time to answer it. *Is civil liability regulation moving away from the risk categories employed in regulatory frameworks (such as the AIA)?* Based on the considerations made in Chapters 2 and 3, this answer, in my opinion, is quite simple: *Yes, it is.*

In the EU, the strategy adopted in the AILD and the rPLD, jointly considered, is significantly different than that of the 2020 Resolution. The 2020 Resolution recommended the adoption of two different civil liability regimes for harm caused by AI systems, with the risk category being the parameter for distinguishing them: high-risk AI systems should be subject to strict liability, while other AI systems should be subject to a fault-based liability regime, with a presumption of fault combined with the reversal of the burden of proof, unless Member States adopted stricter national laws.

Considering the latest version of the AILD and the rPLD, the landscape of AI liability in the EU currently navigates through two distinct yet interconnected systems: one system is focused on a quasi-strict (product) liability regime largely harmonised among the Member States, equally applicable to all AI systems, albeit with significant limitations in terms of scope (covered by the rPLD); the other system remains significantly unharmonised, relying on the diverse rules of national tort law in each Member State, with a unified approach regarding some procedural mechanisms (covered by the AILD).

The rPLD does not expressly reference the AIA or its risk-based categories. It applies to software in general and, in theory, equally to all AI systems, regardless of the category in which they were included under the AIA. The AILD directly references the AIA and, indeed, uses the risk categories as a parameter for establishing different procedural rules for disclosing information and for certain situations involving a rebuttable presumption of causation, but that's

pretty much as far as it goes. The idea of using risk categories for establishing strict liability has, for now, been abandoned (or at the very least postponed¹⁷⁶) in the EU.

In Brazil, throughout negotiations in Parliament, the civil liability provisions in the BAIB have distanced themselves considerably from the categories of AI systems. As a result, although the risk-based approach might still play a role in civil liability for AI in Brazil, it appears to be a more limited one for the time being.

Initially, the BAIB had opted for an approach that resembled the 2020 Resolution, establishing strict liability for excessive and high-risk AI systems and rebuttable presumptions of fault and causation for other AI systems under certain situations. However, the amended version of the BAIB, as of 18 June 2024, reinforces existing tort law and product liability law - neither specifically designed nor adapted for AI – and specifies that the assessment of the liability regime applicable must be done in the concrete case considering the AI system’s autonomy and its ‘degree of risk’, along with the nature of the agents involved. Moreover, the provisions on reversal of the burden of proof have no relation to the risk categories; they apply when the victim proves they are vulnerable or when the characteristics of the AI system (regardless of the risk category) make it excessively burdensome for the victim to prove the civil liability requirements.

However, that doesn’t mean the risk categories have become irrelevant when considering liability. In the EU, the treatment of claims involving high-risk AI systems is currently different than those involving non-high-risk AI systems. In summary, the four significant differences are the following:

- (i) The possibility of the claimant requesting the disclosure of evidence to the provider or user of a high-risk AI system and establishing a rebuttable presumption of fault in case of non-compliance.
- (ii) The need to demonstrate specific non-compliance with the AIA’s requirements for high-risk AI systems in order for the rebuttable presumption of causation to come into play.

¹⁷⁶ Article 5 of the AILD requires the European Commission to review the AILD’s application and present a report, within five years after the end of the transposition period, assessing the effectiveness of Articles 3 and 4 in achieving the AILD’s objectives, specifically evaluating the appropriateness of no-fault liability rules for claims against operators of certain AI systems and the need for insurance coverage (AILD (n 29) Art 5).

- (iii) The possibility of the defendant in a claim involving a high-risk AI system to avoid the presumption of causation if they can demonstrate that sufficient evidence and expertise is reasonably accessible for the claimant.
- (iv) The requirement that proving causation is excessively challenging for the presumption of causality to come into play in claims involving non-high-risk AI systems.

In Brazil, the courts, when assessing the liability regime applicable, must consider the AI system's autonomy and its 'degree of risk', along with the nature of the agents involved. This assessment of the 'degree of risk' is critical because, as addressed in Chapter 4.1, strict liability applies under Brazilian law when the activity typically conducted by the tortfeasor, by its nature, represents a risk to others (this is often referred to as a 'dangerous activity'¹⁷⁷).¹⁷⁸

However, the 'degree of risk' is not said to be precisely the risk categories listed in the BAIB. The meaning of what it is or what the courts should consider when assessing such a degree of risk is still unclear. Unless this term is clarified in future versions of the BAIB, the courts will probably take into account the risk category in which a specific AI system has been included, but this will not be sufficient, per se, for establishing a different liability regime. For example, a court may conclude that a high-risk AI system is not subject to strict liability under the sole paragraph of Article 927 of the Brazilian Civil Code because the defendant's activity, in that specific case, does not typically, by its nature, represent a risk to others.

This brings us to our second question: *Should the regulation of AI liability distance itself from the risk categories established in regulatory frameworks?* Now, that is more complicated to answer.

While analysing the AILD, Jan de Bruyne and others argue that '[t]he clear link with and reference to the AI Act for the content of certain concepts *is a step in the right direction to ensure consistency*'.¹⁷⁹ Philipp Hacker, although in a different context, also recognises that direct reference to the AIA ensures consistency in the legislation.¹⁸⁰ Consistency in regulation is an important attribute which should not be overlooked or taken for granted. Consistency leads to legal certainty, generating trust in the legal system and the regulation.

¹⁷⁷ Sérgio Cavalieri Filho, *Programa de Responsabilidade Civil* (16th edn, Grupo GEN 2023) 5.

¹⁷⁸ Brazilian Civil Code (n 151), Art 927 (sole paragraph).

¹⁷⁹ Bruyne and others (n 117) 4 (emphasis added).

¹⁸⁰ Hacker (n 31) 9.

Safety and liability are, as stated in the Explanatory Memorandum of the AILD, ‘two sides of the same coin’.¹⁸¹ They complement and ‘reinforce each other’.¹⁸² While the AIA aims to reduce risks by ensuring safety and protecting fundamental rights, these risks will not be eliminated, and that is where the liability rules come in.¹⁸³ Liability rules also play an essential part in providing an economic incentive to comply with safety rules.¹⁸⁴ Drawing from that, it is at least desirable that the parameters for regulating safety and liability, as two sides of the same coin, are similar.

However, as Philipp Hacker pointed out, consistency for the sake of consistency would be pointless.¹⁸⁵ While ensuring coherence between the AI Act and liability regimes is important, it is not the ultimate goal, especially when there are valid reasons to differentiate. The AIA focuses on broader societal risks without granting specific rights to affected individuals, whereas a damage liability regime must account for individual differences and specificities.¹⁸⁶ Risks from AI systems can impact individuals unevenly; even if an application does not qualify as high-risk under the AI Act, it may still pose significant risks to a few individuals.¹⁸⁷ This discrepancy highlights the need for an effective liability and compensation system that addresses individual risks, even if the overall societal risk is deemed low.¹⁸⁸

Adopting another approach, Baris Soyer and Andrew Tettenborn argue that the liability regime should be determined by the claimant’s specific interests at stake rather than the degree of abstract risk.¹⁸⁹ They claim that it is crucial to consider the various protected interests when differentiating between strict and fault liability, as different harms - such as personal injury, property damage, and financial loss - may require different legal treatments.¹⁹⁰ While broad strict liability for property damage might not be advisable, limited exceptions, such as for self-driving vehicles, should be considered.¹⁹¹ Therefore, risk categories from the AIA should not

¹⁸¹ Explanatory Memorandum to the AILD (n 29) 3.

¹⁸² *ibid.*

¹⁸³ *ibid.*

¹⁸⁴ *ibid.* 4.

¹⁸⁵ Hacker (n 31) 9.

¹⁸⁶ *ibid.*

¹⁸⁷ *ibid.*

¹⁸⁸ *ibid.*

¹⁸⁹ Soyer and Tettenborn (n 56) 4.

¹⁹⁰ *ibid.*

¹⁹¹ *ibid.*

be directly transplanted into the AILD without considering individual-specific risks and ensuring adequate remedies for those affected.¹⁹²

The process of classifying AI systems is itself complicated and may give rise to uncertainties and discussions as to whether a specific AI should be included in one or another risk category. The prolonged discussion, both in the EU and in Brazil, about the risk categories in the regulatory framework proves per se that this approach is complex. In this context, another issue is that harmed individuals may need help to determine whether their claims fall within the high-risk category so that they can benefit from the procedural mechanisms established by the AILD.

In conclusion, while using risk categories provides more legal certainty, particularly for developers and providers, it introduces complexity and potential arbitrariness, in addition to ignoring the nuances of individual cases. This approach, although coherent, might not fully address the specific risks associated with different AI systems and, at the same time, impose burdensome obligations on AI developers and providers. Therefore, there may be more effective and fair solutions than relying solely on risk categories to determine liability.

A sectoral approach to AI liability might offer a more tailored and practical framework. By focusing on specific sectors such as healthcare, transportation, or finance, regulations can be better aligned with each field's unique risks and requirements. This would allow for a more practical application of liability rules, addressing the distinct challenges posed by AI in different contexts.

An alternative approach could involve establishing a general clause of strict liability, supplemented by specific parameters for courts to assess. While this method might initially introduce some uncertainty - given that courts would need to interpret these parameters in the context of actual cases - it offers significant advantages. It circumvents the problems related to using a rigid and closed abstract classification method, by allowing flexibility and attention to the nuances of individual cases.

Moreover, setting parameters that take into account specific practices and contexts would reinforce the principle of deterrence, combining again the features of safety and liability regulation. This balance between flexibility and deterrence could foster both innovation and

¹⁹² *ibid.*

responsibility in the development and deployment of AI. The latest version of the BAIB seems to be heading in this direction, although the concept of ‘degree of risk’ still remains unclear. However, it is yet too early to tell if this approach will be adopted in the final text and how it will be interpreted by the courts.

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